

D. 4.1 – International cooperation initiatives between Europe and Africa on advancing gender participation in energy transition

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on advancing gender participation in energy transition

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Acronym Full Name

AEEP	Africa-EU Energy Partnership
AREI	African Renewable Energy Initiative
AU	African Union
AUC	African Union Commission
CCA	Clean Cooking Alliance
CCSE	Partnership on Climate Change and Sustainable Energy
CDC	Centers for Disease Control and Prevention
DfID	Department for International Development
EACREEE	East African Centre for Renewable Energy and Energy Efficiency
EAPP	Eastern Africa Power Pool
EEEP	ECOWAS Energy Efficiency Policy
ECOW-GEN	ECOWAS Programme on Gender Mainstreaming in Energy Access
EIB	European Investment Bank
EIT	European Institute of Innovation and Technology
ElectriFI	Electrification Financing Initiative
ENERGICA	ENERGICA Project
EREP	ECOWAS Renewable Energy Policy
EU	European Union
GCCA	Global Climate Change Alliance
GEC	Gender Equality Commission
GEMS	Global Partnership for Girls' and Women's Education in STEM
GWNET	Global Women's Network for the Energy Transition
JETP	Just Energy Transition Partnerships
LEAP-RE	Long-Term Joint European Union - African Union Research and Innovation Partnership on Renewable Energy
REAP	Regional Energy Access Programme
RECP	Africa-EU Renewable Energy Cooperation Programme
REESAP	Renewable Energy and Energy Efficiency Strategy and Action Plan
SACREEE	SADC Centre for Renewable Energy and Energy Efficiency
SADC	Southern African Development Community
SDGs	Sustainable Development Goals

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SE4All Sustainable Energy for All

STEM Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics

STEMM Science, Technology, Engineering, Mathematics, and Medicine

STI Science, Technology, and Innovation

TVET Technical and Vocational Education and Training

UK PACT UK Partnering for Accelerated Climate Transitions

UNESCO United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization

WAPP West Africa Power Pool

Executive Summary

The objective of this work package is to exploit opportunities for international cooperation between Europe and Africa to advance women in the efforts to create just and fair socio-technical systems. The collaboration between the European Union (EU) and African nations in the pursuit of sustainable development, climate change solutions, and gender equality is essential to achieving successful outcomes. The array of EU-Africa programmes, agreements, and initiatives embodies a shared commitment to address pressing global challenges of energy transition, climate resilience, and gender inclusivity. The partnership between the EU and African countries is marked by concerted efforts in promoting renewable energy and sustainable energy infrastructure. Joint initiatives focus on enhancing access to clean energy, promoting technological innovation, and bolstering energy security across the African continent. These collaborations aim to facilitate a transition towards low-carbon and resilient energy systems and ensure accessibility to reliable and sustainable energy sources. The EU and Africa jointly spearhead initiatives aimed at combating climate change and fortifying resilience to its adverse impacts. Integrated climate adaptation and mitigation strategies, including capacity-building programmes, innovative climate finance mechanisms, and knowledge-sharing platforms, underscore the commitment to address climate vulnerabilities and energy poverty. A critical facet of EU-Africa partnerships lies in the opportunities to jointly advance gender equality and women's empowerment, most lately created through Horizon Europe projects. Collaborative projects emphasize inclusive policies, socio-economic empowerment, and educational opportunities to elevate the role of women in sustainable development, climate resilience, and energy transition initiatives. Most of these programmes or projects do not explicitly state gender inclusiveness but their main goals are geared towards the attainment of the Agenda 2030 of the Sustainable Development Goals and the AU Agenda for 2063 which captures gender equality and climate action. The study gathers interesting results that support gender consideration in energy transition for climate adaptation and mitigation.

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background and objectives of EU-Africa cooperation

The relationship between the European Union (EU) and African nations has over the last decade undergone significant transformation, marked by a shared commitment to address critical global challenges. Central among these collaborative efforts are multifaceted programmes, agreements, and initiatives aimed at fostering sustainable development, combating climate change, and advancing gender equality across Africa. The EU and Africa have collaborated on many occasions in energy transition as both regions are striving to maximise efforts to achieve their clean energy targets through renewable energy cooperation, climate change mitigation strategies, and gender empowerment initiatives. These multifaceted efforts reflect the shared commitment of both regions to not only confront pressing challenges but also seize opportunities for sustainable growth and development.

The Gender-STI research project on gender equality in Science, Technology, and Innovation (STI) between 2019 and 2020, co-financed by the European Commission's Horizon 2020 program, aimed to address gender gaps in scientific research and innovation, particularly focusing on gender equality in scientific careers, gender balance in decision-making, and the integration of gender dimensions in Research and Innovation (R&I) content. The analysis revealed that only 4% (354 out of 11,215 documents) of STI policies addressed gender and inclusiveness issues, with the integration of the gender dimension in R&I content significantly less addressed compared to the other two priorities by the European Commission. The Gender STI project examined 528 international bilateral and multilateral STI agreements from 1961 to 2021 and reported that only 15% (81 agreements) included gender-related content, indicating that gender content in STI agreements is far from mainstream, albeit showing an increasing trend from 2015 onwards. The most frequently used terminology in STI agreements is 'gender equality,' often aimed at improving gender equality or promoting gender balance in STI-related activities, followed by phrases related to empowering women's participation in STI. Moreover, while women and girls are commonly viewed as specific targets of the activities addressed in STI agreements, the inclusion and intersectionality aspects were also mentioned to some extent in these agreements.

The European Union's latest flagship research and innovation programme, Horizon Europe, includes initiatives aimed at supporting energy transition efforts in Africa, whilst also imposing gender equality criteria in the provision of funding. These initiatives recognize the importance of addressing energy challenges on the African continent to achieve sustainable development goals, promote economic growth, and mitigate climate change. Horizon Europe plays a crucial role in advancing energy transition efforts in Africa by leveraging combined Africa's and Europe's expertise, resources, and networks to support sustainable and inclusive development on the continent. Through collaborative research, capacity building, technology transfer, and policy support, Horizon Europe contributes to building a resilient and low-carbon energy future for Africa. Gender (in)equality considerations are essential for ensuring that energy-related initiatives and programmes are inclusive, equitable, and sustainable. Horizon Europe promotes gender mainstreaming across all its funding areas, and requires that all benefiting organisations have in place a Gender Equality Plan or

equivalent intervention measures. It recognizes that addressing gender disparities and empowering women are essential for achieving the goals of a clean, affordable, and accessible energy future for all.

The 2030 United Nations Sustainable Development Agenda for energy transition (SDG7) is gender blind in that it has no gender indicators or targets even though the goal aims to ensure universal access to affordable, reliable, sustainable, and modern energy services. Furthermore, analyses of interlinkages between different goals and in particular involving SDG7 have historically marginalised the relevance of SDG 5, which targets gender equality and empowerment of women. However, research evidence shows that integrating gender considerations into energy transition initiatives is crucial for several reasons including creating more equitable, sustainable, and resilient energy systems that benefit everyone, leaving no one behind.

The relationship between the EU and African countries to advance gender equality is also facilitated through joint participation in multilateral organisations such as UN Women and UNESCO. UN Women is the United Nations entity dedicated to gender equality and the empowerment of women. It was established in 2010 to accelerate progress towards gender equality and the realization of women's rights worldwide. UN Women plays a crucial role in catalyzing action and mobilizing support for gender equality and women's empowerment globally, contributing to the achievement of the Sustainable Development Goals and the realization of the vision of a world where women and men enjoy equal rights, opportunities, and dignity.

In 2012, the EU signed a Memorandum of Understanding with UN Women and UNESCO (United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization) to enhance dialogue, foster exchanges of best practices, and work together towards shared priorities, including promoting gender equality in all areas of work, as enshrined in the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development.

UNESCO is actively engaged in promoting education and gender equality, including initiatives related to energy and gender. UNESCO advocates for girls' education and works to address barriers that prevent girls from accessing quality education, including those related to gender stereotypes, poverty, and lack of infrastructure. By empowering girls through education, UNESCO contributes to enhancing their opportunities for leadership, economic empowerment, and participation in decision-making processes, including in the energy sector. UNESCO promotes Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics (STEM) education for girls and women to bridge gender gaps in STEM fields, including those related to energy and sustainable development. Through initiatives such as the Global Partnership for Girls' and Women's Education in STEM (GEMS), UNESCO supports efforts to improve access to STEM education, provide mentorship and role models, and challenge stereotypes and biases that deter girls from pursuing careers in STEM, including in energy-related disciplines. UNESCO advocates for gender-responsive Technical and Vocational Education and Training (TVET) programmes that provide girls and women with skills and competencies for employment and entrepreneurship opportunities in the energy sector and other fields. UNESCO works with governments, educational institutions, and other stakeholders to develop curricula, training materials, and teaching methodologies that promote gender equality and women's participation in TVET programmes related to renewable energy, energy efficiency, and sustainable development.

The Gender Summit-Africa is a regional platform that convenes stakeholders from across Africa to discuss and address gender disparities and promote gender equality in science, technology, engineering, mathematics, and medicine (STEMM) fields. It is part of the global Gender Summit, which was created as an outcome from an EU-funded project, genSET. Each Africa-focused summit is organised around a theme of specific importance to Africa and provides a forum for researchers, policymakers, educators, industry leaders, civil society organizations, and other stakeholders to share knowledge, best practices, and innovative strategies for advancing gender equity and inclusion in STEMM disciplines. The 2023 GS-Africa used as the theme: Africa's Energy Transition and Green Deal through the Gender Lens.

Other EU initiatives of relevance to collaboration include the European Parliament's call for cooperation between EU and Africa on SDGs; the entrepreneurship, and leadership training programmes, e.g., EIT's InnoEnergy and EIC's Women in Leadership; and the Global Women's Network for the Energy Transition (GWNET) mentoring programme for women in renewable energy.

This report assesses the landscape of the EU-Africa collaborative endeavours, highlighting the aim of each programme and the pivotal role of the joint programmes in sustainable energy transition and gender considerations for an equitable future for both continents. It provides information on the concerted efforts undertaken by the EU and the African nations toward common goals of sustainable development, energy transition, climate action, and gender parity. The review is crucial for understanding the scope and impact of the collaborative efforts between the EU and African countries in addressing climate change and promoting gender equality in the context of sustainable development, and the energy transition efforts. This analysis supports the basis of the gEneSys project to advance knowledge on the gender and energy nexus. The report will ultimately guide the development of Guidance Notes with evidence on gender perspective in energy transition to communicate to the UN High-level Dialogue on Energy, and to support UN Women efforts to advance energy transition in Africa.

1.2 Needs assessment

There is a paucity of literature on the gender-energy nexus, which signifies a critical gap in understanding the intersectionality between gender dynamics and energy access, distribution, and utilization. Despite the recognized importance of gender considerations in energy policy and programming, there remains a limited body of research that comprehensively examines these linkages. Traditionally, the energy sector has been (and still is) dominated by technical and engineering perspectives, often overlooking the social dimensions, including gender dynamics. This has led to a lack of attention to how energy policies and interventions can affect men and women differently. In many contexts, there is a lack of sex-disaggregated data on energy access, usage patterns, and the impact of energy interventions on diverse gender groups. There is also a lack of disaggregated data on attitudes to 'green economies', energy poverty and energy needs. Without robust data, policy makers face challenges in developing gender-sensitive intervention measures and assessments of impact. Research on gender-energy nexus requires interdisciplinary approaches that combine social science methodologies with technological energy studies. However, there is a lack of standardized methodologies and frameworks for conducting gender-

sensitive energy research, leading to biases in evidence and knowledge. Governments and policymakers tend to prioritize other aspects of energy policy, such as infrastructure development and energy security, and marginalise gender equality and social justice considerations. Limited awareness among policy makers and researchers about the importance of integrating gender perspectives into research and energy policies and programmes further exacerbates the risks that the policy ambitions to achieve just and fair outcomes in energy transition efforts will not be achieved. When these challenges are addressed, and proactive steps are taken to integrate gender perspectives into energy research and practice, stakeholders in the energy transition ecosystem can contribute to a more inclusive, equitable, and sustainable energy transition. The EU-Africa partnerships and programmes on the energy transition, such as the LEAP-RE programme, have the capacity to promote inclusion of gender considerations in project design, and improve the research and development methodologies and frameworks for assessment of need and impacts. The assessment is crucial for ensuring that energy planning, policy-making, and project implementation take into account the diverse needs, priorities, and perspectives of women and men.

1.3 Theoretical Framework

1.3.1 *Conceptualizing the nexus of climate change, energy, and gender*

The intersection of climate change, energy, and gender is an important and multifaceted issue that encompasses both challenges and opportunities. Gender disparities exist in access to clean energy sources such as electricity, clean cooking facilities, and renewable energy technologies (Oparaocha and Dutta 2011). Women and girls, particularly in rural and marginalized communities, often bear the primary responsibility for household energy tasks, such as cooking and collecting fuelwood. Lack of access to clean and efficient energy sources not only affects their health and well-being but also limits their educational and economic opportunities. Addressing gender inequalities in energy access requires designing and implementing policies and programmes that consider the specific needs, preferences, and priorities of women and girls. This may involve increasing access to clean cooking technologies, promoting women's participation in decision-making processes related to energy planning and management, and providing training and support for women entrepreneurs in the renewable energy sector (Malhotra et al 2004).

On the contrary, the energy sector, including both traditional fossil fuel industries and emerging renewable energy sectors, has historically been male-dominated. Women are underrepresented in technical and leadership roles in the energy industry and in the energy-related research and development, facing barriers such as gender bias, lack of access to training and education, and limited networking opportunities. Promoting gender diversity and inclusion in the energy sector is essential for fostering innovation, improving decision-making, and promoting social and economic development. This may involve implementing policies to support women's career advancement in the energy sector, providing mentorship and networking opportunities, and addressing workplace culture and biases.

Integrating gender considerations into climate change adaptation and resilience-building efforts is essential for ensuring that responses are effective, equitable, and

sustainable. This may involve conducting gender-sensitive vulnerability assessments, empowering women as agents of change and resilience in their communities, and promoting women's participation in decision-making processes related to climate adaptation and disaster risk reduction. Promoting gender-inclusive approaches to renewable energy development can help maximize the benefits of clean energy transitions for women and girls. This may involve incorporating gender considerations into renewable energy policies and programmes, supporting women's entrepreneurship in the renewable energy sector, and ensuring that renewable energy projects are designed and implemented in consultation with local communities, including women and marginalized groups.

Addressing the gender dimensions of climate change and energy requires a holistic and intersectional approach that considers the diverse experiences, needs, and priorities of women, men, and gender-diverse individuals, as well as minority social groups. We can build more resilient, inclusive, and sustainable societies when we promote gender equality and women's empowerment in climate change and energy initiatives.

Gender

According to the World Health Organisation, gender refers to the socially constructed norms, roles and relations that a given society uses as appropriate categories when referring to men and women. It is a different concept to biological sex, although in many contexts biological and gender difference interact, e.g., differences in the consequences for women's and men's health of climate change effects or pollution from traditional cookstoves. The social gender stereotypes determine what is expected, permitted, and valued in a woman or a man in a specific context. Children as young as 2-years old learn through observing the behaviours of the people around them to recognise the prevalent societal gender stereotypes used to differentiate women from men (Eisenberg et al 1996; Powlishta et al 2001).

Gender sensitivity

Across United Nations institutions, gender sensitivity is defined as the understanding and consideration of socio-cultural norms and discriminations in order to acknowledge the different rights, roles and responsibilities of women and men in the community and the relationships between them. SDG 5 calls for the equitable engagement of both women and men in all areas of societal endeavours, and embodies the need to focus on redressing existing imbalances as both the fundamental human right and a necessary foundation for a peaceful, prosperous and sustainable world. The African Union Gender Policy seeks to provide the basis and to eliminate barriers to gender equality in Africa and to guide gender equality actions for the continent in implementing other global commitments. Gender equality is a key principle of EU policies, implemented through legally binding agreements between Member States. These agreements provide opportunities for addressing economic and socio-cultural inequalities at institutional, national, and cross European levels through structural changes. It has an added focus on facilitating the creation of an enabling structural environment of policy frameworks for gender equity and women's empowerment. The Gender Equality Commission (GEC) of the Council of Europe - the leading human rights organisation that includes 46 member states, 27 of which are members of the European Union - was established to help ensure the mainstreaming of gender equality into all policies of its member countries and to bridge the gap between

commitments made at international level and the reality of women's lives compared to those of men in Europe.

Studies have reported differences between women and men in their energy use-related behaviours (Carlsson-Kanyama & Lindén 2007) (e.g., forms and types of travel, choice of electrical consumables). Evidence is also available to show that women (and children) experience the effects of climate change, such as high temperatures, more intensely than men (Vincent et al 2010; Akinsemolu & Olukoya 2020). Studies of the benefits of electrification in the Global South have pointed to the dominant position that men can have in household energy-use and purchases decisions by prioritising their rather than the women's needs (e.g., obtaining a television over installing lighting in the kitchen). A study on gender roles and responses to energy transition in Africa found that women who lacked either short-term or long-term economic support from male relatives, or who disagreed with the husband's or family elders on decisions, faced difficulties in accessing energy (Musango 2022). They also faced the heavy burden of the cost of seeking efficient energy despite often limited access to resources at their disposal. It is possible that in settings where there are different social and ethnic groups, and consequently different languages and norms, communication on efficient energy usage may be more difficult for women than for men.

1.3.2 Review of literature on gender roles in energy access and climate change adaptation

Socio-culturally determined, gender roles are significant in determining adoption and access to sustainable energy resources and in shaping responses to climate change adaptation. Efforts to promote adoption of energy saving stoves have often assumed that these decisions are purely a women's affair (Alston 2014) and tended to overlook the cultural traditions that fixing a broken stove was a 'men's responsibility' (Ngarava et al 2022; Johnson et al 2020). It is generally recognised that women and girls are disproportionately affected by energy poverty (Pachauri and Rao 2013). In many regions of the Global South, women are primarily responsible for household energy tasks such as collecting fuel, cooking, heating, and fetching water. Limited access to modern energy services not only exacerbates impact of poverty by hindering women's opportunities for empowerment and socio-economic development, and taking control over their lives..

Climate change intensifies existing gender inequalities and disproportionately affects women and girls, particularly in environmentally and economically vulnerable communities. Women are often more dependent on natural resources and ecosystem services for their livelihoods (Robinson 2016; Agarwal 1989), such as agriculture and water resources, making them more susceptible to climate-related risks such as crop failures, water scarcity, and natural disasters. Gender disparities in access to resources, decision-making power, and adaptive capacities further amplify women's vulnerability to climate change impacts (Eastin 2018). Women should play essential roles in driving the transition to sustainable energy systems and climate resilience. As primary users and managers of household energy, the involvement of women in decision-making processes related to energy planning, infrastructure development, and technology adoption is crucial for ensuring that energy solutions are gender-responsive and meet the needs of diverse communities (Lane et al 2021; Clancy et al

2019). Empowering women as agents of change (Figure 1.1) in the energy sector can contribute to more inclusive and sustainable development outcomes.

Women often play key roles in community-based adaptation strategies that build resilience to climate change impacts (Reid et al 2013; Clarke et al 2019). Their knowledge of local ecosystems, traditional practices, and social networks can inform adaptation planning and contribute to the development of context-specific solutions. Integrating gender considerations into adaptation policies and programmes can enhance their effectiveness and ensure that they address the differentiated needs and priorities of women, men, and marginalized groups. Figure 1.1 provides the linkages between climate change, energy and women.

Fig 1.1: Linkages between climate change, energy and women. Source: UN Women Africa

2. METHODOLOGY

2.1 Approach to data collection and analysis

Initial information was sought from the internet using google search engine to get a broad overview of the partnerships and programmes on energy transition in Africa. A follow up assessment was done by contacting the institutions and project managers for documentation of the programmes. For each project or programme, the approach differed depending on the nature of it. For each program, the level of details presented in the report depends on the availability of information and the willingness of the institution to provide the information. The programmes which are still active or ended in the last five years are assessed. The objective is to understand the gender consideration in the energy programmes, projects, policies and framework established between EU and Africa on energy transition. A literature review is

conducted to identify existing studies, reports, policy documents, and academic publications relevant to EU-Africa cooperation on energy, climate, and gender. The assessment process also explored databases, institutional websites, research repositories, and grey literature sources. A number of documents including EU policy documents, bilateral agreements between the EU and African countries or regional blocs, project reports, evaluations, and other relevant materials were reviewed.

The analysis consisted of content analysis from the extracted information. For each programme, a gender analysis is conducted to assess the extent of gender mainstreaming and the extent to which gender considerations are integrated into energy and climate initiatives. We examined the gender-specific objectives, activities, outcomes, and participation levels. A case study is conducted for programmes and partnership to assess gender sensitivity at the regional level. We synthesized the findings from the literature review, document analysis including financial analysis and gender analysis. Key findings and recommendations were prepared for enhancing EU-Africa cooperation on energy transition, climate action, and gender equality.

2.2 Analytical Dimensions

In this section, we present the crucial aspects of Policy Alignment, Gender Mainstreaming, and Finances within EU-Africa climate and energy initiatives, emphasizing the necessity for these initiatives to resonate with global frameworks and integrate gender perspectives comprehensively.

Policy Alignment: The analysis scrutinizes the alignment of EU-Africa initiatives with pivotal international frameworks such as the Paris Agreement, Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), and commitments to gender equality. It seeks to uncover the degree of harmony or discord between the stated policy objectives and the actual implementation strategies of these initiatives. This alignment is fundamental, as it not only validates the initiatives' relevance to global agendas but also their effectiveness in addressing specific challenges pertinent to energy, climate change, and gender equality within the EU-Africa context.

Gender Mainstreaming: This part of the analysis concentrates on the incorporation of gender considerations throughout the lifecycle of the programmes - from their inception and design through to execution and assessment. It evaluates the extent to which gender analysis, the gathering of gender-disaggregated data, and the application of gender-responsive methodologies are embedded in the fabric of energy and climate interventions. The critical examination of these initiatives for gender mainstreaming is instrumental in ensuring that they are not just gender-aware but actively contribute to dismantling gender disparities, therefore facilitating more inclusive and equitable outcomes in the energy and climate sectors.

Financial analysis: This ideally expands on the financial commitments and allocations made towards the gender-focused aspects of the initiatives. It details the specific financial investments directed at empowering women within the energy and climate change sectors, outlines any dedicated funds for gender-responsive energy projects, and highlights financial strategies aimed at addressing gender disparities. The financial landscape sheds light on the economic underpinnings that support gender inclusivity in EU-Africa energy and climate initiatives.

3. EU-AFRICA BILATERAL PARTNERSHIPS AND PROGRAMMES

3.1 Partnerships

The EU-Africa Partnership serves as a key framework for cooperation, focusing on bringing Africa and Europe closer together by strengthening economic cooperation and promoting sustainable development. The partnerships emphasize a multi-actor approach, engaging EU and African Union Member States, non-state actors, civil society organizations, youth bodies, economic and social actors, and the private sector. A joint vision for 2030, adopted at the 6th EU-AU Summit, outlines commitments to investment, peace and security, migration and mobility, and multilateralism. The partnership also prioritizes gender equality and inclusiveness, as evidenced by initiatives like the Africa-Europe Foundation, which facilitates stakeholder exchanges on major challenges, including those related to gender.

3.1.1 Africa-EU Energy Partnership (AEEP)

The AEEP is a long-standing framework for strategic dialogue between Africa and the European Union (EU) to address the challenge of accessing affordable and reliable energy services on both continents, with a specific emphasis on increasing investments in energy infrastructure in Africa. It is financed by the European Commission and Germany. The AEEP aims to promote access to sustainable energy services, renewable energy, and energy efficiency in Africa. It focuses on policy dialogue, capacity building, and investment facilitation. The AEEP is one of the partnerships adopted under the Joint Africa-EU strategy (JAES) which was signed by 80 African and European Heads of State and Government at the Lisbon Summit in 2007. The partnership renewed their commitment at the 6th EU-AU Summit in Brussels in February 2022 where an investment package of about £150 billion was announced to support the two continents common ambition for attaining Agenda 2030 for sustainable development and the African Union Agenda 2063. The investment package is part of the Commission's Global Gateway strategy to support investments in sustainable infrastructure worldwide. As the framework aims to address the attainment of Agenda 2030 and the African Union Agenda 2063, it is by extension, clamouring for climate action as well as making energy services affordable and accessible for all irrespective of one's gender or resources.

3.1.2 Just Energy Transition Partnerships (JETP)

Just Energy Transition Partnership (JETP) is a global collaboration that seeks to help emerging economies transition away from fossil energy into clean energy while addressing social and economic challenges. The JETPs targeted seven countries, with partnerships concluded for Vietnam, Indonesia, South Africa and Senegal. One of such is the Just Energy Transition Partnership with South Africa (JETP South Africa) which the EU signed, together with the governments of France, Germany, the United Kingdom and the United States of Africa, on 2 November 2021. This partnership is targeted at providing financing of more than €3 billion to support South Africans on their climate commitments. JETP Senegal was signed in Paris on 22 June 2023 with France, Germany, the EU, the United Kingdom and Canada. In the partnership, €2.5 billion was mobilised to contribute to accelerating the deployment of renewable

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energies and increase its share in installed capacity to 40% of Senegal's electricity mix by 2030. The JETPs primarily focus on decarbonizing energy systems in emerging countries and providing financial support for initiatives like replacing coal plants with cleaner energy sources and improving electrical grids. The idea is to implement the energy transition in partnership in an equitable and inclusive approach regarding its social consequences. These partnerships stress on energy transition implemented in an equitable and inclusive manner with regard to its social consequences. For instance, in the national JET Implementation Plan for South Africa, the word “gender” appeared four times (JET Implementation Plan 2023 – 2027, p. 240, p.291 & p.297) as an indicator of JET skills.

3.1.3 Partnership on Climate Change and Sustainable Energy (CCSE)

The Partnership on Climate Change and Sustainable Energy is a joint effort between the European Union and the African Union to combat climate change and promote sustainable energy practices. The partnership aims to mobilize resources and knowledge to inform policy making across Europe and Africa, focusing on climate change mitigation and adaptation strategies. The partnership supports renewable energy and energy efficiency and issues related to climate change and sustainable energy such as capacity building and human capital development. It dedicates €84 million to advance climate adaptation and renewable energy in Africa. This partnership operates through two pillars; firstly, it focuses on climate adaptation and mitigation, aiding countries in achieving Paris Agreement goals. Secondly, it concentrates on integrating renewable energy and enhancing energy efficiency, aiming to address Africa's low electrification rate, which stood at 35% in 2017, and even lower in rural areas, below 20%.

As part of the efforts to attain the 17 SDGs by 2030 and African Union Agenda of 2063, a roadmap drafted by experts which was then adopted in 2017, emphasizes the importance of low-emission and net-zero economies. In the roadmap, four areas for research and capacity building were identified, one of them is “promote climate strategies and action plans”. This section considers gender inclusion highlighting an example that early warning mechanisms should be gender-responsive. The roadmap also stated that there should be “Special support to young and promising researchers, in line with principles of gender equity and the inclusion of socially vulnerable groups”. This partnership has limited gender consideration.

3.1.4 Long-Term Joint European Union - African Union Research and Innovation Partnership on Renewable Energy (LEAP-RE)

The Long-Term Joint European Union - African Union Research and Innovation Partnership on Renewable Energy (LEAP-RE) is a collaborative initiative between the European Union (EU) and the African Union (AU) aimed at promoting research, innovation, and cooperation in renewable energy across Europe and Africa through joint implementation of research, innovation, and capacity-building activities. This partnership seeks to address common energy challenges, accelerate the transition to sustainable energy systems, and contribute to achieving the SDGs and the objectives of the Paris Agreement on climate change. It also seeks to advance renewable energy solutions to combat climate change and promote sustainable practices. The partnership involves over 30 countries and over 200 research partners from both

regions, working together to develop innovative renewable energy solutions and for long-term collaboration in renewable energy.

The partnership is expected to reduce fragmentation by aligning existing bilateral and multilateral frameworks. The partnership involves 85 research partners from both regions, working together to develop innovative renewable energy solutions and foster long-term collaboration in renewable energy. There are currently about 31 renewable energy research and innovation ongoing projects in their portfolio, but none is gender specific. The closest gender consideration is in the LEAP-RE project named the "Solar Induce" which states "helping to protect women and children from collecting wood for cooking and becoming ill due to respiratory problems" as one of its expected impacts.

3.15 UK Partnering for Accelerated Climate Transitions (UK PACT)

The UK Partnering for Accelerated Climate Transitions (UK PACT) is a partnership of UK and countries with high emissions reduction potential aimed at supporting them in their efforts to transition to low-carbon, climate-resilient economies. The UK PACT programme focuses on supporting the development of renewable energy projects and promoting sustainable energy access across the countries. It has the Gender, Equality and Social Inclusion (GESI) considerations as an integral part of the programme. The primary aim of the GESI is to enhance opportunities for women, advance equality for marginalized groups, and limit discrimination in climate mitigation projects. In Africa, UK PACT has programmes in Nigeria, Kenya and South Africa.

3.2 Programmes

3.2.1 Africa-EU Renewable Energy Cooperation Programme (RECP)

The Africa-EU Renewable Energy Cooperation Programme (RECP) is a multi-donor programme that supports the development of markets for renewable energy in Africa. It was launched by more than 35 African and European Ministers and Commissioners under the Africa-EU Energy Partnership (AEEP). The Africa-EU Renewable Energy Cooperation Programme (RECP) promotes renewable energy markets and investments in Africa through technical assistance, capacity building, and financing mechanisms. The programme includes the provision of information on African energy markets, identification of project opportunities for joint project and business development in Africa as well as facilitation of access to finance. The RECP focuses on meso-scale renewable energy investments that is based on an integrated approach of interlinked activities organised in four Action Areas (Policy Advisory, Private Sector Cooperation, Access to Finance, and Innovation and Skills Development) geared towards enabling and triggering investment. Each Action Area is targeting a crucial factor for the success of efficient markets. RECP also provides policy advisory services and supports local skills development by working with technical and vocational training institutions and academia. Specific details on how it addresses women's involvement or focuses on gender issues within its implementation are not available.

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3.2.2 The Africa-EU Green Energy Initiative

The Africa-EU Green Energy initiative was proposed by the EU at the 6th EU-AU Summit as part of the Global Gateway Investment package to support large-scale sustainable electrification programmes in Africa. The main goal of the initiative is to transform and guide the various economies in Africa through increasing the number, businesses and industries accessing affordable, modern and sustainable energy services, providing support for investment in renewable energy generation and promoting energy efficiency. The Africa-EU Green Energy Initiative aims to provide at least 100 million people with electricity access by 2030 and €3.4 billion in EU grants delivered through Team Europe to support renewable energy, energy efficiency, the just transition, and the greening of the local value chains. It proposes also to promote new opportunities for cooperation on clean hydrogen production in Africa through four modes of cooperation namely research, regulation, investments, and trade. The initiative is said to support large-scale sustainable electrification programmes by addressing three priorities; however, none of these priority areas is gender specific.

3.2.3 The Electrification Financing Initiative (ElectriFI)

The Electrification Financing Initiative (ElectriFI) is an over EUR 275 million impact investment facility funded by the European Union and managed by European Development Finance Institutions. It is committed to increasing access to clean energy in developing countries including countries in Africa. ElectriFI aims to support investments that increase and/or improve access to modern, affordable and sustainable energy services. This initiative proposes that the said projects must lead to new and improved connections for populations living in rural, under-served areas or regions experiencing unreliable power supply in developing countries. ElectriFI supports Les Soleils du Bénin for example, with a EUR 3.1 million investment, ensuring sustainable energy accessibility to over 3000 households and businesses in Benin. It plays a crucial role in addressing energy poverty, spurring economic development, and empowering communities through sustainable energy access. In the 2022 annual report of the ElectriFI in their attempt to bridge the gender gap (women empowerment) stated that 76% of their portfolio qualifies under the “2X Challenge” financing for women. However, gender is not considered a priority area in the Electrification Financing Initiative (ElectriFI).

3.2.4 African Renewable Energy Initiative (AREI)

The Africa Renewable Energy Initiative (AREI) is an Africa owned and African led project aimed at transforming the continent's vast renewable energy potential. AREI is mandated under the African Heads of State and Government of Climate Change (CAHOSCC). This initiative targeted at achieving not less than 10 GW of new renewable energy capacity by 2020 and mobilising Africans generation potential to 300 GW by 2030. In support of these objectives, ten international partners including the EU and G8 nations pledged to mobilise \$10billion between 2015-2020. The EU contributed €1.5 billion under the European Funds for Sustainable Development (EFSD) and the EU Electrification Financing Initiative (ElectriFI) to facilitate new investments, resulting in the addition of at least 5 GW of renewable energy capacity by 2020. The AREI achieved the 10GW objectives a year ahead of schedule due to the adoption of 200 projects of which the EU financed 78 with €1.1 billion. The initiative provides a

general acknowledgment of the importance of social inclusion and gender equality in its strategic approaches but has no gender specific strategy.

3.2.5 West Africa Power Pool (WAPP)

The WAPP is a collaborative effort among West African countries. It covers 14 of the 15 countries of the regional economic block and is in partnership with the EU and other agencies to create a unified electricity market. It aims to enhance energy security, increase access to electricity, and promote the integration of renewable energy sources across the region by improving cross-border and reliable flows of electricity in ECOWAS Member States. The West Africa Power Pool (WAPP) involves countries from the Economic Community of West African States (ECOWAS), which includes 15 member countries: Benin, Burkina Faso, Cape Verde, Côte d'Ivoire, The Gambia, Ghana, Guinea, Guinea-Bissau, Liberia, Mali, Niger, Nigeria, Senegal, Sierra Leone, and Togo. These countries collaborate to establish a reliable power grid for the region and work towards integrating their national power systems into a unified electricity market. The programme aligns with the commitment of ECOWAS to integrate gender equality in energy access but has no specific gender considerations.

3.2.6 Eastern Africa Power Pool (EAPP)

The Eastern Africa Power Pool (EAPP) is a regional organization established in 2005 to coordinate cross-border power trade and grid interconnection among nations of the Eastern Africa region. It is also to promote cooperation and integration in the electricity sector among Eastern African countries. The primary goal of the EAPP is to facilitate the development and operation of efficient, reliable, and affordable electricity infrastructure and services in the region. The EAPP currently has thirteen (13) member countries that signed the Intergovernmental Memorandum of Understanding (IGMOU) and fourteen utilities that signed the Inter Utility Memorandum of Understanding (IUMOU). It has seven strategic objectives, and none is focused on gender considerations.

3.2.7 Sustainable Energy for All (SE4All)

The SE4All was launched in September 2011 by the UN Secretary General with focuses on promoting energy efficiency, renewable energy, and universal access to electricity, with a particular emphasis on addressing energy poverty. The SE4All Africa Hub was launched in May 2013 in Marrakesh and is hosted by African Development Bank (AfDB). The Hub provides guidance to African governments and energy stakeholders. It delivers technical assistance, fosters networking and communication, and contributes towards finance mobilisation. The EU partners with SE4All to improve energy access and sustainability across Africa. The program actively integrates gender as a cross-cutting issue to specifically empower women through enhanced energy access and participation in the energy sector.

3.2.8 ENERGICA

ENERGICA is a EU-Funded project which brings together 11 Africa-based and 17 European partners to foster collaboration between the two continents on energy access and sustainable energy development. The project seeks to develop innovative

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nanogrids in rural Madagascar, low-tech efficient biogas systems and water purification demonstrated in peri-urban Sierra Leone and solar powered e-mobility solutions in urban Kenya. The target beneficiary stands at 1500 local stakeholders across Africa. The project started on 1 November 2021 and ends on 31 October 2025. The total cost was € 12,348,175.75 and the EU contribution was € 9,999,370.39. Technische Universität Berlin, Germany does the project coordination. One of the objectives of the policy is "Mainstreaming gender in renewable energy related issues in particular associated with women's productive roles".

3.2.9 Global Climate Change Alliance (GCCA)

The Global Climate Change Alliance (GCCA) is an European Union initiative. It was launched in 2007 by the European Commission to promote dialogue and cooperation on climate change between the EU, Developing Countries and Least Developed Countries & Small Island Developing States (SIDS), the hardest hit by the effects of climate change. Following the Paris Agreement on Climate Change in 2015, the initiative expanded to cover the middle income countries and extended support for implementing the Nationally Determined Contributions (NDCs) hence now Global Climate Change Alliance Plus (GCCA+). The GCCA/GCCA+ act as a platform to exchange experience and dialogues between the EU and developing countries on climate policies. It also provides financial and technical support to partner countries to integrate climate change in their policies and budgets. The GCCA/GCCA+ budget amounts to EUR 750 million for the period 2007–2020. This includes contributions by the EU of EUR 737.5 million (with EUR 317.5 million contributed by the EU in the first phase (2007-14) and EUR 420 million contributed by the EU in the second phase (2015-20)). Many of the GCCA+ actions integrate participative and community-based solutions with gender focus. In total, GCCA+ has 33 gender related actions such as training of women in the energy sector, gender mainstreaming in climate, capacity building and micro-finance. Furthermore, the evaluations of GCCA+ programmes include a G-marker (Gender Equality Policy Marker), an accountability tool used for tracking resource allocations of donors to promote gender equality.

3.2.10 Clean Cooking Alliance (CCA)

Clean Cooking Alliance (CCA) is a global organization dedicated to addressing the issue of household air pollution caused by traditional cooking methods, such as open fires and inefficient stoves, which pose significant health and environmental risks, particularly in low- and middle-income countries. The CCA works to accelerate the adoption of clean cooking solutions by advocating for policies and investments that support the widespread use of clean and efficient cookstoves and fuels. The organization collaborate with governments, businesses, and civil society organizations to improve access to clean cooking technologies, reduce carbon emissions, and enhance the health, safety, and well-being of communities around the world to improve livelihoods, empower women, and combat climate change.

4. CASE STUDIES: EU COLLABORATIONS WITH AFRICAN REGIONAL BODIES

4.1 Economic Community of West African States (ECOWAS)

The ECOWAS community is committed to promoting gender equality. It adopted a Gender Strategy (2010- 2020) which will enable the ECOWAS region to move towards a participatory approach involving men and women as equal stakeholders in its developmental agenda and equal beneficiaries in the outcomes of the region's developmental efforts. There are a number of energy policies that support gender integration into programmes in the ECOWAS region.

4.1.1 ECOWAS Energy Efficiency Policy (EEEP)

The ECOWAS Energy Efficiency Policy (EEEP) is aligned with broader initiatives aimed at mainstreaming gender in energy access and sustainability. While the specific gender components within the EEEP may not be detailed in the provided information, ECOWAS has developed programmes and policies to address gender disparities in energy access and efficiency. This idea was birthed in 2008 at the 61st Session of the ECOWAS Council of Ministers meeting and was officially launched in 2010. The main objective was to double the annual improvement in energy efficiency in the region to match up to that of the world. Specifically, the policy targeted the implementation of efficiency measures that free-up 2000 MW of generation capacity by 2020, through lighting, cooking, building code, finance and standards, and labels.

4.1.2 ECOWAS Renewable Energy Policy (EREP)

The ECOWAS Renewable Energy Policy (EREP) underscores the commitment to fostering renewable energy across the region, with a clear vision towards achieving universal access to electricity by 2030 and providing sustainable domestic energy services for cooking. It is an European Union directive on renewable energy efficiency potentials of the Africa region to foster its integration within the block. This policy is in partnership with the European Union, UNIDO, Spanish Cooperation and the World Bank Group. It was adopted by ECOWAS Ministers of Energy at the ECOWAS High Level Energy Forum held on the 24-31 October 2012 in Accra-Ghana. The initiative is part of a broader effort to increase the share of renewable energy in the overall electricity mix of the ECOWAS region, thereby contributing to job creation and business development throughout the renewable energy technology value chain. The gender component of the EREP and related initiatives stress the importance of gender equality and mainstreaming in energy access. It aims at promoting job creation and business development throughout the value chain of renewable energy technologies (e.g. manufacturing, installation and construction, operation and maintenance).

4.1.3 ECOWAS Programme on Gender Mainstreaming in Energy Access (ECOW-GEN)

The ECOWAS Programme on Gender Mainstreaming in Energy Access (ECOW-GEN) stands as a cornerstone initiative of the ECOWAS Centre for Renewable Energy and Energy Efficiency (ECREEE), dedicated to overcoming obstacles to the equitable

involvement of women and men in advancing energy access across West Africa. Central to this programme is the recognition of the imperative to integrate gender considerations into various facets of energy governance, including policy formulation, legislative drafting, and the planning and execution of energy initiatives. The ECOW-GEN aims to foster parity in energy development, ensuring that both women and men have equal access to resources and opportunities within the energy sector.

Despite the challenges in obtaining specific details about the gender component within the ECOWAS Energy Efficiency Policy (EEEP) from available sources, it is evident that ECOWAS acknowledges the pivotal role of gender equality in realizing sustainable energy objectives. The ECOW-GEN initiative confirms a dedication to mainstreaming gender perspectives into energy policies and endeavors. This acknowledges a broader recognition that attaining energy efficiency and access objectives necessitates confronting both technical and social impediments, including those stemming from gender disparities.

Since its inception, the ECOW-GEN has remained steadfast in its commitment to maximizing women's capacity as providers and distributors of energy services throughout the ECOWAS region. This initiative acknowledges that empowering both women and men is indispensable for effectively implementing regional policies on renewable energy and energy efficiency. These policies are pivotal in advancing the Sustainable Energy for All (SE4ALL) objectives in West Africa.

ECOW-GEN operates under the fundamental belief that achieving the Sustainable Energy for All (SE4ALL) objectives in West Africa hinges upon the empowerment of women in the energy sector. The programme is designed to steer ECOWAS Member States towards incorporating gender perspectives into various stages of energy governance, including policy development, legislative processes, and the planning and execution of energy initiatives. By doing so, ECOW-GEN aims to advance gender equality in energy access, ensuring that energy policies and projects leverage the capabilities of both women and men. The involvement of women in ECOW-GEN encompasses various dimensions.

Knowledge sharing and capacity building

ECOW-GEN facilitates learning and knowledge exchange among women's groups and associations involved in energy initiatives within and beyond the region. Through initiatives like the Women's Technical Exchange Program, women's groups are paired with experts in different energy technologies, and financial support is provided to facilitate capacity-building activities.

Addressing energy poverty with a gender lens

ECOW-GEN recognizes the critical role of women in combating energy poverty in the region. By ensuring their participation in renewable energy and energy efficiency policies and projects, the programme acknowledges the untapped potential of women as energy service providers and aims to leverage their contributions to alleviate energy poverty.

Promotion of women-led energy projects

ECOW-GEN supports women-led energy projects that have the potential to make a significant impact on energy access and sustainability. This initiative not only

empowers women but also harnesses their expertise and leadership to drive growth and sustainability in the energy sector.

The strategies and activities of ECOW-GEN underline the importance of gender equality and women's empowerment in achieving sustainable energy goals in West Africa. ECOW-GEN contributes to broader objectives of energy access, efficiency, and sustainability within the ECOWAS region as the initiative prioritizes the involvement and leadership of women in the energy sector. Despite challenges in accessing specific details about the gender component within the ECOWAS Renewable Energy Policy (EREP) through available sources, it is evident that ECOWAS recognizes the pivotal role of gender equality in sustainable energy development. By integrating gender considerations into renewable energy policies and projects, ECOWAS is taking steps toward fostering more inclusive and equitable energy development in the region.

4.2 The Southern African Development Community (SADC)

The European Union is actively involved in supporting energy programmes and initiatives in the Southern African Development Community (SADC) region, including those aimed at promoting gender equality and women's empowerment in the energy sector.

4.2.1 SADC Regional Energy Access Programme (REAP)

One of the key energy programmes for the SADC region is the SADC Regional Energy Access Programme (REAP). This programme focuses on improving access to modern and sustainable energy services for all people in the SADC region, particularly those living in rural and underserved areas. The programme may be inclusive but not gender sensitive as there is not specific information on it. The goal is to address the region's energy challenges and promote sustainable energy development.

4.2.2 The Renewable Energy and Energy Efficiency Strategy and Action Plan (REEESAP)

The Renewable Energy and Energy Efficiency Strategy and Action Plan (REEESAP) is a comprehensive framework developed by the Southern African Development Community (SADC) to promote the sustainable development and utilization of renewable energy sources and energy efficiency measures across the region. The REEESAP aims to address energy security concerns, promote economic growth, mitigate climate change impacts, and improve access to modern and sustainable energy services for all people in the SADC region. The REEESAP serves as a guiding framework for advancing renewable energy and energy efficiency initiatives in the SADC region, contributing to sustainable development, climate resilience, and energy access for all people in the region. It aims to accelerate the transition to a low-carbon and sustainable energy future in Southern Africa.

4.2.3 SADC Centre for Renewable Energy and Energy Efficiency (SACREEE)

The SADC Centre for Renewable Energy and Energy Efficiency (SACREEE), was established by REEESAP with a purpose to promote the implementation of the REEESAP

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(SADC, 2016). SACREEE serves as a regional hub for coordination, capacity building, knowledge sharing, and technical assistance in renewable energy and energy efficiency, with the overarching goal of accelerating the transition to a sustainable energy future in Southern Africa. This includes conducting policy assessments, facilitating stakeholder consultations, and advocating for supportive policy frameworks at the regional and national levels. SACREEE supports the development of renewable energy and energy efficiency markets in the SADC region by promoting investment opportunities, facilitating business matchmaking, and providing market intelligence and analysis. The center also serves as a knowledge hub, facilitating the exchange of information, experiences, and lessons learned among stakeholders in the region. SACREEE contributes to the achievement of regional energy goals and targets, as well as the broader objectives of the SADC Energy Protocol and the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals. Information on gender activities of the center is not clearly stated.

4.2.4 East African Centre for Renewable Energy and Energy Efficiency (EACREEE)

The East African Centre for Renewable Energy and Energy Efficiency (EACREEE) is a regional institution focused on promoting renewable energy and energy efficiency in East Africa. It was established to address energy challenges and harness the potential of sustainable energy sources. EACREEE facilitates collaboration, capacity building, and knowledge sharing among East African countries. The center supports the development and implementation of policies, regulations, and strategies to accelerate the adoption of renewable energy technologies and improve energy efficiency practices. The center has eight activities and services but none has a specific focus on gender consideration.

5. INTEGRATION OF GENDER CONSIDERATIONS IN EU-AFRICA PARTNERSHIPS

Incorporating gender perspectives into partnership frameworks, policies, programmes, and projects can address gender disparities, promote inclusive development, and harness the full potential of all individuals. The assessment of gender considerations in EU-Africa partnerships through partnerships and programmes involves ensuring that gender equality and women's empowerment are mainstreamed into partnership agreements, programmes, and action plans. Integrating gender considerations in EU-Africa partnerships and programmes requires dedicated funding and resources for gender-specific activities and initiatives. This includes allocating financial resources for projects that explicitly target gender equality outcomes, such as women's economic empowerment programmes, gender-responsive infrastructure projects, and initiatives to address gender-based challenges. The table 5.1 summarizes the gender considerations in the EU-Africa partnerships and programmes.

Table 5.1: Summary of gender considerations in the EU-Africa partnerships and programmes.

No.	Initiative	Description	Gender Consideration
1	Africa-EU Energy Partnership (AEEP)	It was established to enhance cooperation between Africa and the EU on energy matters, aiming for universal access to affordable, sustainable, and modern energy services in Africa. It emphasizes the joint action of African and European states towards energy transition and development, focusing on inclusive growth and job creation.	The framework is gender neutral.
2	Just Energy Transition Partnerships (JETP)	This is a collaborative effort aiming to support countries in transitioning from fossil fuel-based energy systems to sustainable, renewable energy sources. They emphasize equitable and inclusive approaches.	The JET Implementation Plan for South Africa has a conscious effort to integrate gender considerations into the development of skills for the energy transition. The inclusion highlights an emphasis on ensuring gender equality and women's participation in the transitioning energy sector, reflecting a commitment that is socially inclusive and equity in the move towards renewable energy sources.
3	Partnership on Climate Change and Sustainable Energy (CCSE)	CCSE is designed to foster sustainable energy solutions and climate change mitigation through research and capacity building. It aims to develop comprehensive climate strategies and action plans that incorporate a broad spectrum of social and environmental considerations.	One of the four areas for research and capacity building in the roadmap considers gender inclusion highlighting an example that early warning mechanisms should be gender-responsive. It also has special support for young and promising researchers, in line with principles of gender equity and the inclusion of socially vulnerable groups.
4	Long-Term Joint European Union - African Union Research and Innovation Partnership on Renewable Energy (LEAP-RE)	This partnership facilitates collaboration between the EU and AU on renewable energy projects to foster sustainable energy solutions across Africa.	The LEAP-RE Solar Induce project is expected to help to protect women and children from collecting wood for cooking and becoming ill due to respiratory problems.
5	Africa-EU Renewable Energy Cooperation Programme (RECP)	Supports renewable energy market development in Africa through technical assistance and financing.	Gender consideration is not explicitly stated.

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No.	Initiative	Description	Gender Consideration
6	Africa-EU Green Energy Initiative	This Initiative aims to catalyze sustainable electrification programmes across Africa.	The Africa-EU Green Energy Initiative does not explicitly outline gender considerations within its primary objectives.
7	Electrification Financing Initiative (ElectriFI)	ElectriFI is an EU-funded impact investment facility aiming to increase clean energy access in developing countries, with a significant focus on Africa. It supports projects that enhance access to modern, affordable, and sustainable energy services.	ElectriFI attempts to bridge the gender gap through its portfolio with 76% of it assigned to the "2X Challenge" financing for women. However, gender is not considered a priority area in the ElectriFI.
8	African Renewable Energy Initiative (AREI)	Aims to accelerate the use of renewable energies in Africa.	AREI acknowledges the importance of social inclusion and gender equality in its strategic approaches, aiming to leverage renewable energy as a tool for equitable development across genders.
9	West Africa Power Pool (WAPP)	Enhances electricity exchange and reliability across West African countries.	WAPP has no gender commitment information but aligns with broader the ECOWAS commitments to integrate gender equality in regional development efforts, focusing on equitable access to energy resources.
10	Eastern Africa Power Pool (EAPP)	Facilitates power system integration and trade in Eastern Africa.	EAPP has no gender considerations but would be reflective of the regional commitment to gender equality.
11	Sustainable Energy for All (SE4All)	Global initiative to ensure access to modern energy services, improve energy efficiency, and increase the use of renewable energy sources.	SE4All actively integrates gender as a cross-cutting issue, aiming to empower women through enhanced energy access and participation in the energy sector.
12	ENERGICA	ENERGICA is an EU-funded project aimed at fostering collaboration between Africa and Europe on sustainable energy development and access. It focuses on innovative solutions like nanogrids in Madagascar, biogas systems in Sierra Leone, and solar-powered mobility in Kenya, benefiting around 1,500 local stakeholders.	One of the objectives of the policy is "Mainstreaming gender in renewable energy related issues in particular associated with women's productive roles", underscoring the project's commitment to gender inclusivity in energy access and sustainability efforts.

No.	Initiative	Description	Gender Consideration
13	Global Climate Change Alliance (GCCA)	The Global Climate Change Alliance (GCCA) is an initiative to integrate climate change into poverty reduction strategies and support the implementation of adaptation and mitigation measures. GCCA+ extends support to middle-income countries and NDC implementation.	It emphasizes participatory solutions and gender focus, integrating 33 gender-related actions like training for women in the energy sector and gender mainstreaming in climate policies, capacity building and micro-finance.
14	ECOWAS Energy Efficiency Policy (EEEP)	Aims to improve energy efficiency across ECOWAS member states.	The policy includes gender perspectives by promoting energy solutions that are accessible and beneficial to all, including specific outreach to empower women and girls in energy-efficient practices.
15	ECOWAS Renewable Energy Policy (EREP)	The EREP is designed to promote the use of renewable energy sources within the ECOWAS region. Its objective is to ensure a sustainable and secure energy supply that supports the economic and social development of member states.	The policy emphasizes the importance of gender equality and mainstreaming in its approach, aiming to ensure that energy projects and policies are inclusive and beneficial to both women and men, highlighting a commitment to addressing gender disparities in the energy sector.
16	ECOWAS Programme on Gender Mainstreaming in Energy Access (ECOW-GEN)	The programme is designed to promote gender equality within the energy sector of ECOWAS member states.	ECOW-GEN focuses on creating equitable opportunities for women in energy-related fields, recognizing their crucial role in achieving sustainable energy access and security.
17	SADC Regional Energy Access Programme (REAP)	REAP aims to enhance access to modern and sustainable energy services across the SADC region, focusing on rural and underserved areas. It supports initiatives that bridge the energy access gap, contributing to economic development and poverty alleviation.	REAP is gender neutral.
18	Renewable Energy and Energy Efficiency Strategy and Action Plan (REEESAP)	Addresses energy security, economic growth, climate change mitigation, and access to sustainable energy in the SADC region.	Specific gender considerations are not detailed.

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No.	Initiative	Description	Gender Consideration
19	SADC Centre for Renewable Energy and Energy Efficiency (SACREEE)	Promotes sustainable energy development in the Southern African region.	SACREEE emphasizes inclusive and sustainable energy access but throughout specific programmes targeting gender equality.
20	Partnering for Accelerated Climate Transitions (UK PACT)	Supports countries with high emissions reduction potential to transition to low-carbon, climate-resilient economies by developing renewable energy projects and promoting sustainable energy access across the countries.	UK PACT has the Gender, Equality and Social Inclusion programme
21	Clean Cooking Alliance (CCA)	Promotes access to clean cooking solutions for households worldwide.	CCA prioritizes initiatives that empower women
22	East African Centre for Renewable Energy and Energy Efficiency (EACREEE)	Supports the development and implementation of policies, regulations, and strategies to accelerate the adoption of renewable energy technologies and improve energy efficiency practices.	The programme has no specific gender consideration

6. FINANCIAL ANALYSIS OF EU-AFRICA CLIMATE AND ENERGY PROJECTS

6.1 Overview of financial allocations to EU-Africa climate and energy projects.

The ENERGICA project, a collaborative effort between 11 Africa-based and 17 European organizations, with a total cost of €12,348,175.75 and an EU contribution of €9,999,370.39, aims to achieve a minimum of 10 GW of new renewable energy capacity by 2020, mobilizing Africa's generation potential to 300GW by 2030. To support these objectives, ten international partners, including the EU and G8 nations, committed to mobilizing \$10 billion between 2015-2020. The EU contributed €1.5 billion under the European Funds for Sustainable Development (EFSD) and the EU Electrification Financing Initiative (ElectriFI) to facilitate new investments, resulting in the addition of at least 5 GW of renewable energy capacity by 2020. The Africa Renewable Energy Initiative (AREI) achieved its 10 GW objectives ahead of schedule, with the EU financing 78 out of 200 projects with €1.1 billion. Furthermore, the ElectriFI, an impact investment facility funded by the EU, supports projects like Les Soleils du Bénin with a EUR 3.1 million investment, ensuring sustainable energy access for over 3000 households and businesses in Benin. The European Investment Bank (EIB) has also

been actively financing renewable energy projects in Africa, committing to USD 16.6 million and announcing a new 2.5 billion euro investment package in November 2021 to support renewable energy, clean transport, and climate adaptation projects in Africa, aiming to accelerate the transition to a low-carbon and climate-resilient economy. In the “Status Report 2017-18 and future perspectives” the Africa-EU Energy Partnership (AEEP) presented a summary of EU energy-related initiatives to Africa and presented in table 6.1. Table 6.2 also provides a summary of funds allocation to programmes.

Table 6.1. European Energy Commitments to Africa 2008 - 16 (\$m)

	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016
EC	0	345	93	166	595	336	267	318	629
EIB	1,242	319	2,292	156	821	588	498	868	509
EU-AITF*							45	82	58
France	331	204	743	791	637	854	1166	1394	994
Germany	299	126	386	288	599	352	1190	682	779
UK**	27	na	21	26	27	29	223	49	34
Other EU						90	549	458	295
Total	1899	994	3535	1417	2679	2249	3937	3851	3298

*included within EIB until 2014. **DfID & CDC. na = not available

6.2 Analysis of funding specifically allocated to gender-focused EU-Africa initiatives.

Funding allocated to gender-focused initiatives is a concerted effort by the European Union (EU) to address gender disparities and promote gender equality in various sectors across Africa. The funding demonstrates the EU's commitment to addressing gender inequalities in the energy sector and promoting women's participation and leadership in the energy value chain. EU funded gender projects amounted to 166 millions within a period of 10 years (2014 - 2023). Figure 6.2 provides some details and the amount of money involved in other key initiatives is also shown in table 6.1.

Figure 6.2. Gender budget of 64 EU-funded projects (2014 - 2023)

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Source: <https://www.gender-sti.org/wp-content/uploads/2023/10/Horizon-EU-RI-Programme.pdf>

Table 6.2: The amount of money involved in other key initiatives

Focus area	Focus area	Amount in involved in the initiatives
Africa-EU Renewable Energy Cooperation Programme (RECP)	Renewable energy markets and investments in Africa. Gender details not specified.	Not specified
Africa-EU Green Energy Initiative	Increasing access to sustainable energy, promoting energy efficiency. Includes a €3.4 billion investment for renewable energy and energy efficiency projects.	€3.4 billion
Electrification Financing Initiative (ElectriFI)	Improving access to clean energy in developing countries. Supported Les Soleils du Bénin with a significant investment.	EUR 275 million total; EUR 3.1 million for Les Soleils du Bénin
African Renewable Energy Initiative (AREI)	Transforming Africa's renewable energy potential. The EU contributed significantly towards the initiative's objectives.	\$10 billion pledged; EU contributed €1.5 billion; additional €1.1 billion for 78 projects
West Africa Power Pool (WAPP)	Enhancing energy security and access in West Africa.	Not specified
European Investment Bank (EIB) Financing	Financing renewable energy projects across Africa.	USD 16.6 million by EIB
Sustainable Energy for All (SE4All)	Promoting energy efficiency, renewable energy, and universal access to electricity.	USD 36.6 million revenues in 2021
ENERGICA	Fostering collaboration on energy access and sustainable energy development between Africa and Europe.	Total cost €12,348,175.75; EU contribution €9,999,370.39
Global Climate Change Alliance (GCCA)	Supporting climate policy dialogue and cooperation, with significant funding for climate actions. Gender-focused actions integrated.	EUR 750 million for 2007–2020; GCCA+ has 33 gender-related actions
Partnering for Accelerated Climate Transitions (UK PACT)	Development of renewable energy projects and promoting sustainable energy access across partner countries.	72 million pounds
Clean Cooking Alliance (CCA)	Clean cooking	Not much information

Focus area	Focus area	Amount in involved in the initiatives
East African Centre for Renewable Energy and Energy Efficiency (EACREEE)	Development and implementation of policies, regulations, and strategies to accelerate the adoption of renewable energy technologies and improve energy efficiency practices.	Not specified

7. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

EU-Africa bilateral partnerships and programmes play a crucial role in advancing cooperation between the two continents, particularly in areas such as energy, climate change, and sustainable development. These partnerships emphasize multi-actor engagement, involving governments, civil society organizations, private sector entities, and other stakeholders to address shared challenges and pursue common objectives. The AEEP, JETP, CCSE, and other initiatives underscore the commitment to promoting renewable energy, energy efficiency, and climate action across Africa. However, while gender equality and inclusiveness are prioritized in some partnerships, such as the like Clean Cooking Alliance, there remains a need for more comprehensive gender mainstreaming in energy and climate initiatives to ensure equitable outcomes for all.

Moreover, the programmes under the EU-Africa Partnership, including the Africa-EU RECP, Africa-EU Green Energy Initiative, and ElectrIFI, contribute significantly to advancing renewable energy access and sustainability in Africa. However, the integration of gender considerations in these programmes varies, with some initiatives demonstrating a stronger focus on gender equality than others. While efforts like the SE4All Africa Hub actively integrate gender as a cross-cutting issue, others like the RECP may benefit from enhanced gender mainstreaming strategies to address gender disparities in energy access and participation.

Furthermore, collaboration with regional bodies such as the ECOWAS and the SADC amplifies the impact of EU-Africa partnerships by leveraging regional cooperation frameworks and promoting collective action. ECOWAS renewable energy programmes aim at promoting sustainable energy practices, enhancing energy efficiency, and increasing renewable energy use. For example, the EEEP focuses on improving energy efficiency across sectors like lighting, electricity distribution, cooking, and buildings, while the EREP aims to increase renewable energy share in the region's electricity mix by 2020 and 2030. Both policies play a crucial role in transforming the energy mix, promoting sustainable development, enhancing energy security, and mitigating climate change impacts. In the status report of the ECOWAS Renewable Energy and Energy Efficiency, one of the objectives is centred on investments in renewable energy and the crucial nexus between energy access and gender. The report also highlighted the fact that energy efficiency can contribute to advancing important social and economic development goals, including gender equality. The report also has a section captioned "Gender and Energy in the ECOWAS Region" where various indicators of gender inequality were taken into consideration for different West African countries (ECOWAS Renewable Energy and Energy Efficiency status report, p.51). The report stated that throughout the region's Member States,

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women are underrepresented in decision-making processes and that as a result, their needs are less often accounted for in policy design and implementation. In response, ECOWAS adopted a Gender Strategy (2010-2020) designed to ensure that women and men act as equal stakeholders in the design, implementation, and benefits of development. The EREP requires every Member State to develop a Gender Action Plan.

Initiatives like the ECOW-GEN and the SACREEE demonstrate the importance of mainstreaming gender perspectives in energy policies and programmes to achieve sustainable and inclusive development outcomes. While progress has been made in advancing EU-Africa cooperation on energy and climate issues, continued efforts are needed to strengthen gender mainstreaming, enhance inclusiveness, and ensure the sustainability of collaborative initiatives for the benefit of both continents.

The detailed analysis of EU-Africa cooperation in energy and climate change initiatives, with a strong focus on gender integration, reveals a complex landscape of opportunities and challenges. These initiatives demonstrate a significant commitment to sustainable development, climate action, and gender equality, aligning with global goals and regional ambitions. However, the incorporation of gender considerations varies across initiatives, highlighting the need for more systematic and explicit integration of gender perspectives to ensure equitable benefits and participation. The financial analysis underscores the substantial investments made towards these initiatives, yet calls for more targeted allocations to explicitly address gender disparities. The document's recommendations propose actionable strategies for enhancing gender integration, advocating for measurable goals, diversified representation, and gender-sensitive funding mechanisms to foster inclusivity. The conclusion emphasizes the essential role of gender equality in achieving sustainable and inclusive energy transitions, urging for continued collaboration, innovation, and commitment to integrating gender considerations into future projects and policies.

8. RECOMMENDATIONS - STRATEGIES FOR ENHANCING GENDER INTEGRATION IN FUTURE PROJECTS AND INITIATIVES.

The following recommendations could help integrate gender considerations in the energy transition and climate change mitigation areas, fostering equality and inclusivity.

- Organizations should implement Gender Equality Plans or adopt dedicated Equality, Diversity and Inclusion (EDI) strategies in energy and climate projects (especially when funded under Horizon Europe), setting measurable goals to tackle gender disparities, including gender-based violence.
- Set realistic participation targets to improve the proportion of women in scientific roles in the projects/programmes funded individually or jointly by the EU and/or African countries
- Advocate for gender-sensitive approaches to project/programme design, implementation, and evaluation of impact.
- Ensure inclusion of gender mainstreaming objectives in policy design and decision-making on energy transition and climate change mitigation interventions.

- Create gender balanced, expert advisory groups with knowledge of gender equality issues and their contextual basis in energy and climate agreements.
- Assess and share experiences of implementing gender-focused actions to make improvements in future collaborative programmes and outcomes.
- Promote understanding of context-sensitive diversity and inclusivity in all aspects of gender equality scientific dialogues on energy and climate.
- Include clauses in international agreements that require considerations of gender equality in activities promoting careers, decision making, and research activities.
- Involve gender experts in the development of research content for international collaborations on energy and climate.
- Organize events to spotlight women's achievements in energy and climate sciences, promoting networking and role modeling.
- Harness the potential of international and cross-sectoral collaborations to accelerate actions on shared concerns and goals.

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3. <http://www.ecreee.org/page/ecowas-program-gender-mainstreaming-energy-access-ecowgen>
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20. AREI | Africa Renewable Energy Initiative
21. EU and partners take work of African Renewable Energy Initiative forward - EU Neighbours
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